

Dawn VIR Sequence report for Ceres Extended Juling (CXJ) (vir_da923)

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ABSTRACT

This document constitutes the official flight operation report for the VIR (Visible and Infrared Mapping Spectrometer) instrument onboard the Dawn spacecraft, specifically covering the commanding and sequencing activities performed for the vir_da923 session. These operations were executed as part of the CXJ phase.

The mission profile focused on the observational sequences for the characterization of the planetary body Ceres, aiming to map its mineralogical features and surface properties.

The report details the generation of the instrument's commanding sequences and the formal verification process. All sequences have been checked against the mission's flight and guideline rules within the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) framework. Furthermore, the VIR SASF files were successfully integrated with the sequences of the other onboard instruments to ensure system-level compatibility and resource management. The final integrated sequences were successfully uploaded and executed on the spacecraft during the scheduled vir_da923 window.

KEYWORDS

VIR • Spectral Instrument • Dawn NASA Mission

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References

- [1] M. de Sanctis *et al.*, "The VIR Spectrometer," *ISSR*, vol. 163, no. 1–4, pp. 329–369, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1007/s11214-010-9668-5.
- [2] A. K. J. Stipanuk, "Spacecraft Activity Sequence File (SASF) Interface.," *Deep Space Mission System (DSMS) Subsystem Software Interface Specification*, 2004.

1. Check list of the sequence vir_cxj_C2Juling_1.r07.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_cxj_C2Juling_1.r07.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIR10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

1.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_cxj_C2Juling_1.r07.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_CXJ_VMLSTART_C2Juling_1	530690880	530690882	2
VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOn_Oxo3	530690940	530691361	421
VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOn_Oxo3	530691540	530702346	10806
VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_Oxo3	530703180	530703220	40
VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Oxo3	530703300	530706456	3156
VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_Oxo3	530706480	530706518	38
VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_Oxo3	530706600	530710200	3600
VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_JO3	530720880	530720920	40
VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_JO3	530721000	530724141	3141
VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_JO3	530724180	530724218	38
VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_JO3	530724300	530724307	7
VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_JO3	530724420	530729820	5400
VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_JO3	530729820	530730120	300
VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOn_JO4	530758138	530758559	421
VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOn_JO4	530758738	530769544	10806
VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_Oxo4	530769598	530769638	40
VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Oxo4	530769718	530772874	3156
VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_Oxo4	530772898	530772936	38
VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_Oxo4	530773018	530776618	3600
VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_JO4	530786878	530786918	40
VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_JO4	530786998	530790139	3141
VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_JO4	530790178	530790216	38
VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_JO4	530790298	530790305	7
VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_JO4	530790418	530795818	5400
VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_JO4	530796718	530797018	300
VIR_CXJ_VMLEND_C2Juling_1	530797078	530797079	1

1.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

2. Check list of the sequence vir_cxj_C2Juling_2.r07.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_cxj_C2Juling_2.r07.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

2.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_cxj_C2Juling_2.r07.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_CXJ_VMLSTART_C2Juling_2	530824856	530824858	2
VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOn_Oxo5	530824916	530825337	421
VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOn_Oxo5	530825516	530836322	10806
VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_Oxo5	530836376	530836416	40
VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Oxo5	530836496	530839652	3156
VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_Oxo5	530839676	530839714	38
VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_Oxo5	530839796	530843396	3600
VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_JO5	530854376	530854416	40
VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_JO5	530854496	530857637	3141
VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_JO5	530857676	530857714	38
VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_JO5	530857796	530857803	7
VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_JO5	530857916	530863316	5400
VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_JO5	530864216	530864516	300
VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOn_JO6	530899686	530900107	421
VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOn_JO6	530900286	530911092	10806
VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_Occator6	530911146	530911186	40
VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6	530911266	530914422	3156
VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_Occator6	530914446	530914484	38
VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_Occator6	530914566	530918166	3600
VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_JO6	530918696	530918736	40
VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_JO6	530918816	530921957	3141
VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_JO6	530921996	530922034	38
VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_JO6	530922116	530922123	7
VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_JO6	530922236	530927636	5400
VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_JO6	530927636	530927936	300
VIR_CXJ_VMLEND_C2Juling_2	530927996	530927997	1

2.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

3. Integrated sequence: da923e.00.filter.rsoc

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the da923e.00.filter.rsoc sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

The VIR instrument was configured to acquire 0 calibration cubes and 24 cubes for IR channel and 0 for VIS channel.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
✓	□	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
✓	□	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
✓	□	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
✓	□	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need

4. Appendix

This appendix contains the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) sequences referenced in this report, along with the SPICE meta-kernel employed for the geometric computations and reference frame transformations.

The following SASF files were processed:

4.1 The sequence: vir_cxj_C2Juling_1.r07.sasf

1	CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015\$\$MARK\$\$;	sasf
2	MISSION_NAME = DAWN;	
3	SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;	
4	DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;	
5	FILE_NAME = vir_cxj_C2Juling_1.r07.sasf;	
6	APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2016-281T00:00:00.000;	

```

7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2016-311T00:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2016-292T08:26:05.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_cxj_C2Juling_1.r07;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$MARK$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT   DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR  sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE      Tue Oct 18 08:26:05 2016
20 *SEQGEN    V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN     2016-281T00:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF    2016-311T00:00:00.000
23 *TITLE     VIR_CXJ_da923_Cycle2_ds829
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *CXJ_DEQUAX_024, 2016-300T00:10:00.000
26 *CXJ_DEQUAX_025, 2016-300T19:04:58.000
27 *CXJ_VIRC02_J03, CXJ_DEQUAX_024+02:20:00
28 *CXJ_VIRC02_J04, CXJ_DEQUAX_025+01:45:00
29 *CXJ_VIRC02_0x03, CXJ_DEQUAX_024-02:35:00
30 *CXJ_VIRC02_0x04, CXJ_DEQUAX_025-03:03:00
31 *EPOCHS_END
32 *Input files used:
33 *File Type Last modified      File name
34 *****
35 $$EOH
36 $$EOD
37
38 request(VIR_CXJ_VMLSTART_C2Juling_1,
39         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0x03-03:27:00,
40         TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_cxj_C2Juling_1 (ds829)",
41         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
42         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
43         KEY, "No_Key")
44
45     activity(1,
46             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
47
48             SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE", "ds829", "ds829.mc
49             fb05")
50     ),
51     note(1,
52         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
53         TEXT,\ "BEGIN SEQUENCE: ds829 - vir_cxj_C2Juling_1"\
54     ),
55 end;
56
57 request(VIR_CXJ_C2Power0n_0x03,
58         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0x03-03:26:00,
59         TITLE, "VIR Power on",
60         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
61         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
62         KEY, "No_Key")
63
64     spawn(1,

```

```

63     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
64     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
65     RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
66 ),
67     note(1,
68     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
69     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2Power0n_0xo3: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
70     ),
71 end;
72
73 request(VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_0xo3,
74     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo3-03:16:00,
75     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
76     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
77     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
78     KEY, "No_Key")
79
80     command(1,
81     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
82     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_0xo3: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
83     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
84     ),
85     command(2,
86     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
87     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_0xo3: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
88     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
89     ),
90     note(1,
91     SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
92     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_0xo3: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
93     waiting."\\
94     ),
95 end;
96 request(VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_0xo3,
97     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo3-00:02:00,
98     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
99     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
100    PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
101    KEY, "No_Key")
102
103    activity(1,
104    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
105    NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_0xo3: Set for opening the cover."\\,
106    VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
107    ),
108 end;
109
110 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3,
111     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo3+00:00:00,
112     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
113     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
114     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
115     KEY, "No_Key")
116
117     command(1,
118     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,

```

```

119 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
120 to perform 64 scan mirror steps"\,
121 VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-144000,139500,4500)
122 ),
123 command(2,
124 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
125 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,66
126 frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
127 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,65,130,5,1,69,66,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
128 ),
129 command(3,
130 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
131 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
132 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
133 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
134 ),
135 command(4,
136 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
137 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
138 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
139 ),
140 note(1,
141 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
142 TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.115 Gibit"\
143 ),
144 command(5,
145 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
146 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
147 to perform 64 scan mirror steps"\,
148 VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-144000,139500,4500)
149 ),
150 command(6,
151 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
152 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,66
153 frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
154 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,65,130,5,1,69,66,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
155 ),
156 command(7,
157 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
158 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
159 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
160 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
161 ),
162 command(8,
163 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
164 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
165 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
166 ),
167 note(2,
168 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
169 TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.230 Gibit"\
170 ),
171 command(9,
172 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
173 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
174 to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,

```

```
170     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-148500,144000,4500)
171   ),
172   command(10,
173     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
174     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
175     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
176     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,67,130,5,1,69,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
177   ),
178   command(11,
179     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
180     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
181     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
182     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
183   ),
184   command(12,
185     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
186     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
187     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
188   ),
189   note(3,
190     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
191     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo3: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
192   ),
193 end;
194 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_0xo3,
195   START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo3+00:53:00,
196   TITLE,"VIR close cover",
197   REQUESTOR,"sfonte",
198   PROCESSOR,"GSC1",
199   KEY,"No_Key")
200
201 activity(1,
202   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
203   NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_0xo3: Set for closing the cover.""\,
204   VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
205 ),
206 end;
207
208 request(VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_0xo3,
209   START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo3+00:55:00,
210   TITLE,"VIR dump data into VR4",
211   REQUESTOR,"sfonte",
212   PROCESSOR,"GSC1",
213   KEY,"No_Key")
214
215 command(1,
216   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
217   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,
218   NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_0xo3: begin data dumping into VR4.""\,
219   VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
220 ),
221 command(2,
222   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
223   NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_0xo3: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
224   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
225 ),
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226     note(1,
227         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
228         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_Oxo3: data volume in VR4 0.359 Gibit.\"\
229     ),
230 end;
231
232 request(VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_J03,
233     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J03-00:02:00,
234     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
235     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
236     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
237     KEY, "No_Key")
238
239 activity(1,
240     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
241     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_J03: Set for opening the cover.\"",
242     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
243     ),
244 end;
245
246 request(VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J03,
247     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J03+00:00:00,
248     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
249     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
250     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
251     KEY, "No_Key")
252
253 command(1,
254     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
255     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J03: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
256     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
257     ),
258     command(2,
259         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
260         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
261         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J03: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"",
262         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
263     ),
264     command(3,
265         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
266         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J03: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"",
267         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
268     ),
269     note(1,
270         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
271         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J03: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit\"\
272     ),
273     command(4,
274         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
275         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J03: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,100
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
276         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,100,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
277     ),
278     command(5,
279         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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280     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
281     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J03: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
282     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
283 ),
284     command(6,
285         SCHEDULED_TIME,\ 00:25:36\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
286         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J03: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
287         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
288     ),
289     note(2,
290         SCHEDULED_TIME,\ 00:00:05\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
291         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J03: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\
292     ),
293     command(7,
294         SCHEDULED_TIME,\ 00:00:01\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
295         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J03: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
296         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
297     ),
298     command(8,
299         SCHEDULED_TIME,\ 00:00:05\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
300         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
301         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J03: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
302         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
303     ),
304     command(9,
305         SCHEDULED_TIME,\ 00:13:06\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
306         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J03: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
307         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
308     ),
309     note(3,
310         SCHEDULED_TIME,\ 00:00:05\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
311         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J03: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
312     ),
313 end;
314
315 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_J03,
316     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J03+00:53:00,
317     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
318     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
319     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
320     KEY, "No_Key")
321
322 activity(1,
323     SCHEDULED_TIME,\ 00:00:00\, FROM_REQUEST_START,
324     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_J03: Set for closing the cover." \,
325     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
326 ),
327 end;
328
329 request(VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0ff_J03,
330     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J03+00:55:00,
331     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
332     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
333     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
334     KEY, "No_Key")
335

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336     command(1,
337         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
338         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J03: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
339         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
340     ),
341     command(2,
342         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
343         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J03: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,
344         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"OFF\",75,2500)
345     ),
346     note(1,
347         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
348         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J03: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
349     ),
350 end;
351
352 request(VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J03,
353     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J03+00:57:00,
354     TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
355     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
356     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
357     KEY, \"No_Key\")
358
359     command(1,
360         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
361         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000\"\\,
362         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J03: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
363         VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
364     ),
365     command(2,
366         SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:29:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
367         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J03: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
368         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
369     ),
370     note(1,
371         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
372         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J03: data volume in VR4 0.718 Gibit.\"\\
373     ),
374 end;
375
376 request(VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_J03,
377     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J03+02:27:00,
378     TITLE, \"VIR Power off\",
379     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
380     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
381     KEY, \"No_Key\")
382
383     note(1,
384         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
385         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_J03: Power off VIR instrument.\"\\
386     ),
387     spawn(1,
388         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
389         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\\"ANY_ENGINE\\,
390         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
391     ),
392     note(2,
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393     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
394     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2Power0ff_J03: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
395     ),
396 end;
397
398 request(VIR_CXJ_C2Power0n_J04,
399     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo4-03:13:00,
400     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
401     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
402     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
403     KEY, "No_Key")
404
405     spawn(1,
406     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
407     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
408     RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
409     ),
410     note(1,
411     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
412     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2Power0n_J04: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
413     ),
414 end;
415
416 request(VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_J04,
417     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo4-03:03:00,
418     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
419     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
420     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
421     KEY, "No_Key")
422
423     command(1,
424     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
425     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_J04: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
426     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
427     ),
428     command(2,
429     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
430     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_J04: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
431     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
432     ),
433     note(1,
434     SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
435     TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_J04: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
436     waiting."\"
437     ),
438 end;
439
440 request(VIR_CXJ_C20penCover_0xo4,
441     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo4-00:02:00,
442     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
443     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
444     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
445     KEY, "No_Key")
446
447     activity(1,
448     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
449     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C20penCover_0xo4: Set for opening the cover."\",
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449     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
450     ),
451 end;
452
453 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4,
454     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo4+00:00:00,
455     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
456     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
457     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
458     KEY, "No_Key")
459
460     command(1,
461         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
462         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
to perform 64 scan mirror steps"\,
463         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-144000,139500,4500)
464     ),
465     command(2,
466         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
467         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,66
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
468         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,65,130,5,1,69,66,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
469     ),
470     command(3,
471         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
472         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
473         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
474         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
475     ),
476     command(4,
477         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
478         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
479         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
480     ),
481     note(1,
482         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
483         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.115 Gbit"\
484     ),
485     command(5,
486         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
487         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
to perform 64 scan mirror steps"\,
488         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-144000,139500,4500)
489     ),
490     command(6,
491         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
492         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,66
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
493         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,65,130,5,1,69,66,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
494     ),
495     command(7,
496         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
497         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
498         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
499         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
500     ),

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501     command(8,
502         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
503         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
504         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
505     ),
506     note(2,
507         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
508         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.230 Gibit\"\\
509     ),
510     command(9,
511         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
512         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
513         to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
514         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-148500,144000,4500)
515     ),
516     command(10,
517         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
518         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
519         frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s\"\\,
520         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",15,67,130,5,1,69,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",4,\"NO_VIR
521     ),
522     command(11,
523         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
524         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000\"\\,
525         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
526         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
527     ),
528     command(12,
529         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
530         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
531         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
532     ),
533     note(3,
534         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
535         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo4: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\\
536     ),
537 end;
538
539 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_0xo4,
540     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo4+00:53:00,
541     TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",
542     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
543     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
544     KEY, \"No_Key\")
545
546 activity(1,
547     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
548     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_0xo4: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
549     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
550 ),
551 end;
552
553 request(VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_0xo4,
554     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo4+00:55:00,
555     TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
556     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
557     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",

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556     KEY, "No_Key")
557
558     command(1,
559         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
560         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,
561         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_0xo4: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
562         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
563     ),
564     command(2,
565         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
566         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_0xo4: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
567         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
568     ),
569     note(1,
570         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
571         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_0xo4: data volume in VR4 1.078 Gbit."\"
572     ),
573 end;
574
575 request(VIR_CXJ_C2openCover_J04,
576     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J04-00:02:00,
577     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
578     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
579     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
580     KEY, "No_Key")
581
582     activity(1,
583         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
584         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2openCover_J04: Set for opening the cover."\",
585         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
586     ),
587 end;
588
589 request(VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J04,
590     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J04+00:00:00,
591     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
592     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
593     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
594     KEY, "No_Key")
595
596     command(1,
597         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
598         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J04: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
599             frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s\"\",
600         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
601     ),
602     command(2,
603         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
604         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
605         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J04: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\",
606         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
607     ),
608     command(3,
609         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
610         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J04: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
611         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
612     ),

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612     note(1,
613         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
614         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J04: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit"\
615     ),
616     command(4,
617         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
618         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J04: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,100
        frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
619         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,100,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
620     ),
621     command(5,
622         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
623         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
624         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J04: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
625         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
626     ),
627     command(6,
628         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:25:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
629         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J04: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
630         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
631     ),
632     note(2,
633         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
634         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J04: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\
635     ),
636     command(7,
637         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
638         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J04: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
        frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s"\,
639         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
640     ),
641     command(8,
642         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
643         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
644         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J04: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
645         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
646     ),
647     command(9,
648         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
649         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J04: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
650         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
651     ),
652     note(3,
653         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
654         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J04: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
655     ),
656 end;
657
658 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_J04,
659     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J04+00:53:00,
660     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
661     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
662     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
663     KEY, "No_Key")
664
665 activity(1,

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666     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
667     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_J04: Set for closing the cover." \,
668     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
669     ),
670 end;
671
672 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J04,
673     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J04+00:55:00,
674     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
675     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
676     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
677     KEY, "No_Key")
678
679     command(1,
680     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
681     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J04: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
682     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
683     ),
684     command(2,
685     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
686     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J04: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime." \,
687     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
688     ),
689     note(1,
690     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
691     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J04: the cryocooling is off." \
692     ),
693 end;
694
695 request(VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J04,
696     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J04+00:57:00,
697     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
698     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
699     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
700     KEY, "No_Key")
701
702     command(1,
703     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
704     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000" \,
705     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J04: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
706     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
707     ),
708     command(2,
709     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:29:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
710     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J04: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
711     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
712     ),
713     note(1,
714     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
715     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J04: data volume in VR4 1.437 Gibit." \
716     ),
717 end;
718
719 request(VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_J04,
720     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J04+02:42:00,
721     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
722     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",

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723     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
724     KEY, "No_Key")
725
726     note(1,
727     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
728     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_J04: Power off VIR instrument."\
729     ),
730     spawn(1,
731     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
732     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
733     RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
734     ),
735     note(2,
736     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
737     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_J04: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
738     ),
739 end;
740
741 request(VIR_CXJ_VMLEND_C2Juling_1,
742     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J04+02:48:00,
743     TITLE, "VIR Sequence End - vir_cxj_C2Juling_1 (ds829)",
744     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
745     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
746     KEY, "No_Key")
747
748     note(1,
749     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
750     TEXT,\ "END OF SEQUENCE: ds829 - vir_cxj_C2Juling_1"\
751     ),
752 end;
753
754 $$EOF

```

The following SASF files were processed:

4.2 The sequence: vir_cxj_C2Juling_2.r07.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_cxj_C2Juling_2.r07.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2016-281T00:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2016-311T00:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2016-292T08:26:06.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_cxj_C2Juling_2.r07;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN     SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT   DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR  sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE      Tue Oct 18 08:26:06 2016
20 *SEQGEN    V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN     2016-281T00:00:00.000

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```

22 *CUTOFF      2016-311T00:00:00.000
23 *TITLE      VIR_CXJ_da923_Cycle2_ds830
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *CXJ_DEQUAX_026, 2016-301T13:59:56.000
26 *CXJ_DEQUAX_027, 2016-302T08:54:56.000
27 *CXJ_VIRC02_J05, CXJ_DEQUAX_026+01:35:00
28 *CXJ_VIRC02_J06, CXJ_DEQUAX_027+00:32:00
29 *CXJ_VIRC02_Occator6, CXJ_DEQUAX_027-01:33:50
30 *CXJ_VIRC02_0xo5, CXJ_DEQUAX_026-03:25:00
31 *EPOCHS_END
32 *Input files used:
33 *File Type  Last modified      File name
34 *****
35 $$EOH
36 $$EOD
37
38 request(VIR_CXJ_VMLSTART_C2Juling_2,
39         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo5-03:14:00,
40         TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_cxj_C2Juling_2 (ds830)",
41         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
42         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
43         KEY, "No_Key")
44
45     activity(1,
46         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
47
48         SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE","ds830","ds830.mc
49         fb04")
50     ),
51     note(1,
52         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
53         TEXT,\ "BEGIN SEQUENCE: ds830 - vir_cxj_C2Juling_2"\
54     ),
55 end;
56
57 request(VIR_CXJ_C2Power0n_0xo5,
58         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo5-03:13:00,
59         TITLE, "VIR Power on",
60         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
61         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
62         KEY, "No_Key")
63
64     spawn(1,
65         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
66         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
67         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
68     ),
69     note(1,
70         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
71         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2Power0n_0xo5: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
72     ),
73 end;
74
75 request(VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_0xo5,
76         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo5-03:03:00,
77         TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
78         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
79         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",

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78     KEY, "No_Key")
79
80     command(1,
81         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
82         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_0xo5: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
83         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
84     ),
85     command(2,
86         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
87         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_0xo5: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN." \,
88         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
89     ),
90     note(1,
91         SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
92         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_0xo5: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
93         waiting." \
94     ),
95
96     request(VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_0xo5,
97         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo5-00:02:00,
98         TITLE, "VIR open cover",
99         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
100        PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
101        KEY, "No_Key")
102
103     activity(1,
104         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
105         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_0xo5: Set for opening the cover." \,
106         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
107     ),
108 end;
109
110 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5,
111     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo5+00:00:00,
112     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
113     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
114     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
115     KEY, "No_Key")
116
117     command(1,
118         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
119         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
120         to perform 64 scan mirror steps" \,
121         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-144000,139500,4500)
122     ),
123     command(2,
124         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
125         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,66
126         frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s" \,
127         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,65,130,5,1,69,66,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
128     ),
129     command(3,
130         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
131         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000" \,
132         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
133         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")

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132     ),
133     command(4,
134         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
135         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
136         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
137     ),
138     note(1,
139         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
140         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.115 Gibit\"\\
141     ),
142     command(5,
143         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
144         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
145         to perform 64 scan mirror steps\"\\,
146         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-144000,139500,4500)
147     ),
148     command(6,
149         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
150         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,66
151         frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s\"\\,
152         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",15,65,130,5,1,69,66,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",4,\"NO_VIR
153     ),
154     command(7,
155         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
156         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000\"\\,
157         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
158         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
159     ),
160     command(8,
161         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
162         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
163         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
164     ),
165     note(2,
166         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
167         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.230 Gibit\"\\
168     ),
169     command(9,
170         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
171         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA
172         to perform 66 scan mirror steps\"\\,
173         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-148500,144000,4500)
174     ),
175     command(10,
176         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
177         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68
178         frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s\"\\,
179         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",15,67,130,5,1,69,68,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",4,\"NO_VIR
180     ),
181     command(11,
182         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
183         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000\"\\,
184         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
185         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
186     ),
187     command(12,

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184     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
185     NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
186     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
187   ),
188   note(3,
189     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
190     TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_0xo5: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\\
191   ),
192 end;
193
194 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_0xo5,
195   START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo5+00:53:00,
196   TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",
197   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
198   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
199   KEY, \"No_Key\")
200
201   activity(1,
202     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
203     NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_0xo5: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
204     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
205   ),
206 end;
207
208 request(VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_0xo5,
209   START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_0xo5+00:55:00,
210   TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
211   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
212   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
213   KEY, \"No_Key\")
214
215   command(1,
216     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
217     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000\"\\,
218     NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_0xo5: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
219     VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
220   ),
221   command(2,
222     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
223     NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_0xo5: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
224     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
225   ),
226   note(1,
227     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
228     TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_0xo5: data volume in VR4 0.359 Gibit.\"\\
229   ),
230 end;
231
232 request(VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_J05,
233   START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J05-00:02:00,
234   TITLE, \"VIR open cover\",
235   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
236   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
237   KEY, \"No_Key\")
238
239   activity(1,
240     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
```

```

241     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2openCover_J05: Set for opening the cover." \,
242     VIR_Cover(vir_cover, "OPEN")
243 ),
244 end;
245
246 request(VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J05,
247     START_TIME, CXJ_VIRC02_J05+00:00:00,
248     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
249     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
250     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
251     KEY, "No_Key")
252
253     command(1,
254         SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:00 \, FROM_REQUEST_START,
255         NTEXT, \ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J05: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F, 1 detector, 50
frame, 15 RepTime, Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s" \,
256         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F", 15, 49, 130, 5, 1, 69, 50, "IR_ONLY", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON", 10, "NO_VI
257     ),
258     command(2,
259         SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
260         COMMENT, \ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000" \,
261         NTEXT, \ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J05: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
262         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
263     ),
264     command(3,
265         SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:13:06 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
266         NTEXT, \ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J05: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
267         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
268     ),
269     note(1,
270         SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
271         TEXT, \ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J05: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit" \
272     ),
273     command(4,
274         SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:01 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
275         NTEXT, \ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J05: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F, 1 detector, 100
frame, 15 RepTime, Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s" \,
276         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F", 15, 49, 130, 5, 1, 69, 100, "IR_ONLY", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON", 10, "NO_V
277     ),
278     command(5,
279         SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
280         COMMENT, \ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000" \,
281         NTEXT, \ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J05: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
282         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
283     ),
284     command(6,
285         SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:25:36 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
286         NTEXT, \ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J05: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
287         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
288     ),
289     note(2,
290         SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
291         TEXT, \ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J05: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit" \
292     ),
293     command(7,
294         SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:01 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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295 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J05: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.600s VIS=0.020s\",
296 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",15,49,130,5,1,69,50,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VI
297 ),
298 command(8,
299 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
300 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000\",
301 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J05: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
302 VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
303 ),
304 command(9,
305 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:13:06\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
306 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J05: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
307 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
308 ),
309 note(3,
310 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
311 TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J05: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"
312 ),
313 end;
314
315 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_J05,
316 START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J05+00:53:00,
317 TITLE,\"VIR close cover\",
318 REQUESTOR,\"sfonte\",
319 PROCESSOR,\"GSC1\",
320 KEY,\"No_Key\")
321
322 activity(1,
323 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:00\",FROM_REQUEST_START,
324 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_J05: Set for closing the cover.\",
325 VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
326 ),
327 end;
328
329 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J05,
330 START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J05+00:55:00,
331 TITLE,\"VIR cryocooler off\",
332 REQUESTOR,\"sfonte\",
333 PROCESSOR,\"GSC1\",
334 KEY,\"No_Key\")
335
336 command(1,
337 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:00\",FROM_REQUEST_START,
338 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J05: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
339 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
340 ),
341 command(2,
342 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
343 NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J05: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\",
344 VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"OFF\",75,2500)
345 ),
346 note(1,
347 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:01\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
348 TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J05: the cryocooling is off.\"
349 ),
350 end;
```

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351
352 request(VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J05,
353     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J05+00:57:00,
354     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
355     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
356     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
357     KEY, "No_Key")
358
359     command(1,
360         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
361         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,
362         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J05: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
363         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
364     ),
365     command(2,
366         SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:29:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
367         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J05: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
368         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
369     ),
370     note(1,
371         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
372         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J05: data volume in VR4 0.718 Gibit."\
373     ),
374 end;
375
376 request(VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_J05,
377     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J05+02:42:00,
378     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
379     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
380     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
381     KEY, "No_Key")
382
383     note(1,
384         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
385         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_J05: Power off VIR instrument."\
386     ),
387     spawn(1,
388         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
389         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ ANY_ENGINE\,
390         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
391     ),
392     note(2,
393         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
394         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_J05: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
395     ),
396 end;
397
398 request(VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOn_J06,
399     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_Occator6-03:13:00,
400     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
401     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
402     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
403     KEY, "No_Key")
404
405     spawn(1,
406         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
407         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ ANY_ENGINE\,
```

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408     RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
409   ),
410   note(1,
411     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
412     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOn_J06: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
413   ),
414 end;
415
416 request(VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_J06,
417   START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_Occator6-03:03:00,
418   TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
419   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
420   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
421   KEY, "No_Key")
422
423   command(1,
424     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
425     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_J06: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
426     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
427   ),
428   command(2,
429     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
430     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_J06: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
431     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
432   ),
433   note(1,
434     SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:00:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
435     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2Cryocooler0n_J06: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
436     waiting."\"
437   ),
438 end;
439
440 request(VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_Occator6,
441   START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_Occator6-00:02:00,
442   TITLE, "VIR open cover",
443   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
444   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
445   KEY, "No_Key")
446
447   activity(1,
448     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
449     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2OpenCover_Occator6: Set for opening the cover."\",
450     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
451   ),
452 end;
453
454 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6,
455   START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_Occator6+00:00:00,
456   TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
457   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
458   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
459   KEY, "No_Key")
460
461   command(1,
462     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
463     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA,
464     SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA to perform 64 scan mirror steps"\",
465     VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-144000,139500,4500)
```

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464     ),
465     command(2,
466         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
467         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,66
         frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s"\,
468         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,65,110,5,1,59,66,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
469     ),
470     command(3,
471         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
472         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
473         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
474         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
475     ),
476     command(4,
477         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
478         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
479         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
480     ),
481     note(1,
482         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
483         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.115 Gibit"\
484     ),
485     command(5,
486         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
487         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA,
         SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA to perform 64 scan mirror steps"\,
488         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-144000,139500,4500)
489     ),
490     command(6,
491         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
492         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,66
         frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s"\,
493         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,65,110,5,1,59,66,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR
494     ),
495     command(7,
496         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
497         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
498         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
499         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
500     ),
501     command(8,
502         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
503         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
504         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
505     ),
506     note(2,
507         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
508         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.230 Gibit"\
509     ),
510     command(9,
511         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
512         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: SP_MODE_4_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_4_END_ALFA,
         SP_MODE_4_STEP_ALFA to perform 66 scan mirror steps"\,
513         VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,20,21,22,-148500,144000,4500)
514     ),
515     command(10,

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516     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
517     NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,68  
518     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,67,110,5,1,59,68,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",4,"NO_VIR  
519     ),  
520     command(11,  
521     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
522     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000\"\  
523     NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\  
524     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
525     ),  
526     command(12,  
527     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:17:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
528     NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\  
529     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
530     ),  
531     note(3,  
532     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
533     TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CubeToVIR_Occator6: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\  
534     ),  
535 end;  
536  
537 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_Occator6,  
538     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_Occator6+00:53:00,  
539     TITLE, "VIR close cover",  
540     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
541     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
542     KEY, "No_Key")  
543  
544     activity(1,  
545     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
546     NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_Occator6: Set for closing the cover.\"\  
547     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")  
548     ),  
549 end;  
550  
551 request(VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_Occator6,  
552     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_Occator6+00:55:00,  
553     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",  
554     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
555     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
556     KEY, "No_Key")  
557  
558     command(1,  
559     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
560     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000\"\  
561     NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_Occator6: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\  
562     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")  
563     ),  
564     command(2,  
565     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
566     NTEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_Occator6: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\  
567     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
568     ),  
569     note(1,  
570     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
571     TEXT,\"VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_Occator6: data volume in VR4 1.078 Gibit.\"
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572     ),
573 end;
574
575 request(VIR_CXJ_C2openCover_J06,
576     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J06-00:02:00,
577     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
578     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
579     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
580     KEY, "No_Key")
581
582     activity(1,
583     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
584     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2openCover_J06: Set for opening the cover."\,
585     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
586     ),
587 end;
588
589 request(VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J06,
590     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J06+00:00:00,
591     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
592     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
593     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
594     KEY, "No_Key")
595
596     command(1,
597     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
598     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J06: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
599     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s"\,
600     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,110,5,1,59,50,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
601     ),
602     command(2,
603     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
604     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
605     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J06: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
606     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
607     ),
608     command(3,
609     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
610     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J06: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
611     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
612     ),
613     note(1,
614     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
615     TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J06: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit"\
616     ),
617     command(4,
618     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
619     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J06: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,100
620     frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s"\,
621     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",15,49,110,5,1,59,100,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_V
622     ),
623     command(5,
624     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
625     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
626     NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J06: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
627     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")

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626     ),
627     command(6,
628         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:25:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
629         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J06: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
630         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
631     ),
632     note(2,
633         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
634         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J06: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit\"\\
635     ),
636     command(7,
637         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
638         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J06: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,50
        frame,15 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.200s VIS=0.020s\"\\,
639         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",15,49,110,5,1,59,50,\"IR_ONLY\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VI
640     ),
641     command(8,
642         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
643         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000\"\\,
644         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J06: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
645         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
646     ),
647     command(9,
648         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:13:06\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
649         NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J06: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
650         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
651     ),
652     note(3,
653         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
654         TEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2PushbroomToVIR_J06: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\\
655     ),
656 end;
657
658 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_J06,
659     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J06+00:53:00,
660     TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",
661     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
662     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
663     KEY, \"No_Key\")
664
665 activity(1,
666     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
667     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CloseCover_J06: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
668     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
669     ),
670 end;
671
672 request(VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J06,
673     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J06+00:55:00,
674     TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler off\",
675     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
676     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
677     KEY, \"No_Key\")
678
679 command(1,
680     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
681     NTEXT,\\"VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J06: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,

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682     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
683 ),
684     command(2,
685         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
686         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J06: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\,
687         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
688     ),
689     note(1,
690         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
691         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2CryocoolerOff_J06: the cryocooling is off."\
692     ),
693 end;
694
695 request(VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J06,
696     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J06+00:57:00,
697     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
698     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
699     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
700     KEY, "No_Key")
701
702     command(1,
703         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
704         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,
705         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J06: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
706         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
707     ),
708     command(2,
709         SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:29:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
710         NTEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J06: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
711         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
712     ),
713     note(1,
714         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
715         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2DumpDataToVR4_J06: data volume in VR4 1.437 Gibit."\
716     ),
717 end;
718
719 request(VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_J06,
720     START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J06+02:27:00,
721     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
722     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
723     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
724     KEY, "No_Key")
725
726     note(1,
727         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
728         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_J06: Power off VIR instrument."\
729     ),
730     spawn(1,
731         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
732         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
733         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
734     ),
735     note(2,
736         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
737         TEXT,\ "VIR_CXJ_C2PowerOff_J06: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
738     ),

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739 end;
740
741 request(VIR_CXJ_VMLEND_C2Juling_2,
742         START_TIME,CXJ_VIRC02_J06+02:33:00,
743         TITLE, "VIR Sequence End - vir_cxj_C2Juling_2 (ds830)",
744         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
745         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
746         KEY, "No_Key")
747
748     note(1,
749         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
750         TEXT,\ "END OF SEQUENCE: ds830 - vir_cxj_C2Juling_2" \
751         ),
752 end;
753
754 $$EOF
```